

Co-funded by the European Union

Digital Educational Network For Cultural
Projects Implementation And Direction

3rd Newsletter

1. Dissemination Activities (September 2017- January 2018)

Den Cupid in Greece

From September to December 2017 a number of dissemination and multiplier events took place making the DEN CuPID project widely known..

On the 19th of October 2017 the European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (E.G.T.C) Amphictyony (associate partner of DEN CuPID) together with the Regional Union of Municipalities of Attica organized a one-day conference at the latter's premises under the title "Local administration meets European Cultural Heritage: Ideas and Actions for European Year of Cultural Heritage 2018". DEN-CuPID partners, such as Time Heritage (with team members Aphrodite Kamara, Cleopatra Ferla and Yorgos Tzedopoulos), the Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO and the University of Patras gave extensive presentations on the importance and potential of cultural heritage for local societies. The latter's collaborator, Ms. Maria Papaconstantinou presented the project DEN CuPID in a lecture under the title: "The importance of local cultural heritage and its enhancement on an European level: the experience of the DEN CuPID project", signed also by Laura Tapini and Panagiota Pantzou as co-authors.

Presentation of the DEN CuPID project by ms. Papaconstantinou

At the conference were invited, apart from members of E.G.T.C Ampictyony and the Regional Union of Municipalities, all the Greek trainees of the project; after the conference the latter were invited at lunch by Time Heritage, in order to get to know each other and to discuss with each other as well as with their “mentors” aspects of the projects that they will implement in the following months.

DEN CuPID trainees at lunch

Audience view at the conference

*Time Heritage team members
Dr. Kleopatra Ferla and Dr. Yorgos Tzedopoulos
present their ideas on the various usages of
municipal libraries.*

*The director of E.G.T.C. Ampictyony
mr. V. Xenos-Gavrielis
welcomes the attendants and
inaugurates the conference*

A second conference, similar in content, was organized by E.G.T.C Amphictyony following an invitation by the Regional Union of Municipalities of Central Macedonia on the 16th of November 2017 in Grand Hotel Palace in Thessaloniki. DEN CuPID was presented by Laura Tapini, collaborator of the University of Patras. The conference was attended by representatives of municipalities in the region of Thessaloniki as well as by several representatives of municipalities-members of E.G.T.C Amphictyony from Greece and Cyprus.

Euromed 2017

Marietta Papakonstantinou from the University of Patras team presented DEN-CuPID and the survey carried out in the context of the project to undergraduate students of the Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies, University of Patras on 7/11/2017 and 10/11/2017.

The project was also presented as a case study in a paper given by Nota Pantzou (University of Patras) on "Πολιτιστικός Σχεδιασμός: Προς μια αποτελεσματική διαχείριση και αξιοποίηση της αρχαιολογικής και ιστορικής κληρονομιάς"/"Heritage Planning and the Efficient Management and Promotion of the archaeological and historical heritage" in the context of the national two day conference with the title "Νέα δεδομένα για την αρχαιολογική και ιστορική κληρονομιά: Ανάδειξη και διαχείριση χώρων και μνημείων στη Δυτική Ελλάδα και τα Ιόνια Νησιά. The conference was held in Corfu between 1st and 2nd of December and was organised by the Department of Archives, Library Science and Museology (Ionian University) and the Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies (University of Patras).

Instants from the presentation of DEN-CuPID at Euromed 2017, University of Thessaly

On the 3rd of December 2017 Yorgos Tzedopoulos and Aphrodite Kamara from Time Heritage presented DEN-CuPID at Euromed 2017, the 2nd Pan-Hellenic Conference of Digitization of Cultural Heritage. The lecture, titled “Digital Content, Communication and Cultural Heritage: towards a global concept of cultural resources in the Digital Era”, expressed a series of questions and thoughts on the new digital culture already extant and presented the paradigm of the crowdsourcing platform #outofrome, created by Futuro Digitale, partner of DEN CuPID in Italy, aiming both at the information of visitors and at the reinforcement of a sense of “ownership” among locals. The platform forms the base of the 3rd workshop of the project which will take place in Italy between the 18th and the 23rd of February 2018. The audience was keen on learning more about the project and particularly about the e-platform for education which is going to be launched soon.

Den-Cupid in Italy

Futuro Digitale association has started a common pattern of cultural entrepreneurship and competence up-skilling through a coordination of municipalities called "[XIII Mountain Community](#)" [an association composed of thirteen municipalities situated in hardly accessible areas]. The first meeting was held on the 30th January 2018 to discuss about the different topics of #Outofrome project and the specific learning pattern to train the youth of the national service scheme of apprenticeship/volunteerism of each tourism office. They will be involved in the development process of the platform, gathering stories from the towns where they leave, learning how to develop storytelling design and projects.

Plus, on the 10th February 2018 Futuro Digitale will present Den-Cupid project and open data for cultural management in Cori municipality theatre. The event is set within the [national week for transparent administration in Italy](#).

Lastly the project has been further disseminated to the following forums and sites:

<https://www.vi-mm.eu/2018/01/10/den-cupid-digital-educational-network-for-cultural-projects-implementation-and-direction/>

<https://www.pluggy-project.eu/media-center/liaisons/>

2. Second Workshop: “Creating a Successful Theme Park: The Mill of Elves Christmas Park in Trikala, Greece”

The second workshop for Den- CuPID (Digital Educational Network for Cultural Projects Implementation and Direction) took place in the city of Trikala, Greece between 4/12 to 7/12 in the Research Center- Tsitsanis Museum. Trainees from Greece, Spain, Italy and Bulgaria participated to this 4 days educational seminar.

The workshop was organized by the Developmental Company of the Municipality of Trikala, E-trikala S.A, who is also the coordinator of the project. The main objectives of this workshop, titled “Creating a Successful Theme Park: The Mill of Elves Christmas Park in Trikala, Greece”, was to present and analyze the Christmas Thematic Park of the Mill of Elves as well as the reasons that lead to its commercial success and the added value and financial benefit that this success had in terms of touristic growth and attraction. In addition, lecturers from the Greek Company Time Heritage, Futuro Digitale (Italy) and the University of Patras conducted sessions in relation to cultural management, marketing and branding.

*Vice Mayor of Sports and Culture
of the Municipality of Trikala,
Mrs. Efi Leventi welcoming the trainees*

*Testing managerial abilities
in creating a Theme Park*

The workshop as well as the participants were welcomed at the first day by the Vice Mayor of Sports and Culture of the Municipality of Trikala, Mrs. Efi Leventi, whereas visits to Meteora, local Museums and the Christmas Park took place during the afternoons. A lecture dedicated to the importance and value of Meteora was conducted by dr. Ioannis Manolis from the Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO.

During these 4 days workshop the trainees had the opportunity to present their own project, to participate in exercises that could test their managerial ability to create their own theme park and also to have an onsite visit to the Mill of Elves.

Visit to Meteora

3. Third workshop

Den-Cupid learning voyage reaches a small town in Italy 30 minutes away from Rome, crossed by the pilgrim route of Southern Francigena and oriented toward sustainable tourism practices. The workshop will focus on open data management for cultural projects, on how to promote immaterial cultural heritage through digital technologies and how to define communication/marketing techniques for cultural heritage and businesses/activities. Different guests as well as different authorities have supported the event, such as Lazio Region, Caetani Foundation and the Latina county wine route. Participants will be involved in a special competition - a Dragons Den-Cupid session to convince “investors” to bid their idea.

4. Platform

One of the project's intellectual outputs is the creation of an Educational platform, that will allow all stakeholders, trainees and people that are interested in learning about cultural management to study on line the educational material prepared by the project's partners and follow tests that will evaluate their level of understanding. Furthermore, the platform will serve as well as a networking space, where participants can communicate and share ideas among themselves or with experts and even attend via live streaming any future workshops. In the following period a small testing period will take place, to test the educational platform on a limited number of participants that will give a valuable feedback before the platform is officially presented to the public

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Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO

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